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Effect of Salicylic Acid on Seed Yield of Indian Mustard Under Terminal Heat Stress Condition

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ABSTRACT

Seeds are the primary planting material for crop production. Climatic abnormalities, especially high temperature during reproductive stage may severely impact seed yield and also reduce the morphological, physiological and biochemical quality, ultimately reducing the field performance and planting value of seed. In present investigation, the impact of heat stress was studied for quality seed production of Indian mustard through application of salicylic acid. The experiment was conducted at Jaguli Instructional Farm, BCKV during 2023-24. The experimental design was Factorial Randomized Block Design (FRBD) consisting of three dates of sowing as first factor and three different doses of Salicylic acid with control as second factor. Application of salicylic acid @400ppm (T3) influenced the plant height (cm) and number of primary branches, number of secondary branches, siliqua number, test weight and seed yield significantly. D1 produced maximum impact with significant variation, except for the character number of seeds siliqua⁻¹. The interaction between sowing date and treatment did not have a significant effect except siliqua number, test weight and seed yield. Seed yield was maximum when salicylic acid was applied @400 ppm (T3) under timely sown crop (D1). It was followed by salicylic acid @200ppm (T2). The maximum influence of salicylic acid @400ppm on seed yield was due to maximum number of siliqua plant⁻¹, number of seeds siliqua⁻¹, and test weight. Under very late sown condition, D3T3 produced maximum seed yield, revealing positive impact of salicylic acid under heat stress condition.

Keywords: Indian mustard, salicylic acid, terminal heat stress, TBM-143

INTRODUCTION

Two thousand years ago, the Greeks, Romans, Indians, and Chinese were aware of rapeseed-mustard. Some ancient texts and literature mentioned it and were cultivated as early as 5000 BC. According to Chang (1968), it was cultivated as early as the Neolithic era. [3] Between 2300 and 1750 BC, mustard seeds were found at Channhu-daro, a part of the Harrapan civilization. Aryan people used brassica species as oil and as sauces. Oil use, however, continued to be more common among non-Aryans. In botany, Indian mustard is called *Brassica juncea* ($2n=4x=36$) while rapeseed is called *Brassica napus* ($2n=4x=38$). The Middle East seems to be the origin of *Brassica juncea* [15,17]. After that, it swiftly expanded throughout Asia, India, Africa, Europe, and the Far East [8]. It had appeared multiple times in different places and with different ancestors. Geographic centres of diversity now include the Caucasus, China, and Eastern India [19]. There are two geographical races of *Brassica juncea*, the Chinese and Indians-which is also corroborated by biochemical and molecular research.

In terms of the output of oilseeds, India ranks fourth globally. Worldwide 625 million tons of oilseeds were produced in 2022–2023 (USDA report, April 2023). India's production only makes up around 10% of global production, despite the country owning 20.8% of the world's oil seed agricultural area. This is because rainfed agriculture is the only option for about 72% of India's oilseed land, which has led to low productivity (<https://www.ibef.org>). According to the Economics & Statistics Division of the Department of Agriculture & Farmers Welfare, rapeseed-mustard cultivation in India occupies approximately 8.06 million hectares of land and yields 14.58 quintals per hectare. Our country contributes significantly to the global rapeseed and

mustard market, producing approximately 11.75 million tons of rapeseed mustard (Fourth advance estimates, 2021–2022), fourth only to the European Union (19.5 million tons), Canada (19 million tons), and China (14.7 million tons) (<https://www.statista.com/statistics/263930/worldwide-production-of-rapeseed-by-country/>). In West Bengal, rapeseed-mustard is grown on 6.1 lakh hectares, yielding 1250 kg/ha and 7.6 lakh tons (Fourth advance estimates, 2021–22, source: Economics & Statistics Division, Department of Agriculture & Farmers Welfare).

In West Bengal, particularly in the southern region, rapeseed-mustard is cultivated after the Kharif rice harvest [6]. The delayed sowing of mustard is caused by the delayed harvesting of kharif rice. Higher temperatures in March and April encourage the seeds to mature forcefully, which prevents late planted mustard crops from accumulating the right amount of dry matter [4]. High temperature stress can impact several aspects of plants, including their morphology, physiology, biochemistry, antioxidant enzyme activity, and the quality metrics of crops [16,20]. When exposed to high temperatures, heat shock proteins (HSPs) and reactive oxygen species (ROS) are produced [1,21]. According to a study, an increase of 1°C in the average growing season temperature could result in a crop yield decline of up to 17%, with the extent of the decline varying depending on the crop, growth stage, and environmental circumstances. Higher temperatures change the photosynthetic activity and have an impact on the physiochemical characteristics and structure of the thylakoid membrane [12]. This generates low yield as well as creates low vigour seed, lower plant population during next season [5]. Various strategies have been employed; nevertheless, the foliar application of nutrients has proven to be more advantageous than the alternatives. It

improves the yield and quality of the seeds.

The utilization of plant growth regulators is acknowledged to be a critical factor in the plant's response to stress [2]. Plant development and growth are complex phenomena that depend on a number of external and endogenous factors. Hormones are an essential component of internal elements that control growth and development. According to Hayat *et al.* (2007), salicylic acid (SA) has been identified as a plant hormone. It functions as an endogenous signalling molecule and is crucial for controlling plant growth (by triggering mitotic activity), [7] development, and interactions with other factors as well as reactions to a variety of abiotic stressors [14]. Along with stomatal movement, thermogenesis, nutrient uptake, flower initiation, ethylene production, and enzyme activities, salicylic acid has a variety of physiological functions in plants [7]. Additional functions linked to SA include abiotic stress tolerance and disease resistance [9]. Diverse plant species have endogenous basal levels of Salicylic acid that vary by several orders of magnitude, and it has been demonstrated that unfavourable climatic conditions can increase endogenous SA levels in plants [18].

Seed plays an important role in green revolution. Oil seed production increased significantly from 1990 due to increase area and adoption of improved variety. Since seed is a low-cost input, the quality of seed is an important factor as is directly influencing plant health, yields and overall productivity. Farmers use certified seed to grow crops that could raise crop yield by enhancing seed replacement rate. During last ten years distribution of quality seed of Rapeseed-Mustard decreased from the base year 2010-11 by 44.4%. Rapeseed-Mustard is a cold season crop that requires specific low temperature with longer

duration for optimum growth, flowering and siliqua development [10]. Due to climate change the duration of cold is short and the crop faces higher temperature during the reproductive period. These have negative impact on production and quality of seed. Chemical growth regulators have been found to ameliorative the negative impact of heat stress. Keeping this background, the present research work was undertaken to study the influence of Salicylic acid in mustard under different date of sowing.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The present experiment was conducted during Rabi season 2023-24 at Jaguli Instructional Farm, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Mohanpur, Nadia. The experiment plot where the field investigation was undertaken, is located 22.95°N latitude, 88.54°E longitude with an altitude of 9.73 m above the mean sea level. The experiment site was under subtropical humid climate, with short winter span. The average rainfall was 1.00 mm, temperature ranged from 30.71°C-10.41°C during the experimental period (Fig. 1). The variety TBM-143 developed at Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya in collaboration with Bhabha Atomic Research Centre (BARC), collected from department of Seed Science of Technology, BCKV. The field experiment comprised of three dates of sowing and four treatment combinations *viz.* D1: Timely sowing (17.11.2023); D2: Late sowing (04.12.2023); D3: Very late sowing (21.12.2023) was considered as first factor and four treatments such as T1: Control, T2: Salicylic acid @200 ppm, T3: Salicylic acid @400 ppm, T4: Salicylic acid @600 ppm was considered as second factor. Salicylic acid was sprayed at the time of 50% flowering. N: P₂O₅: K₂O was applied @ 100:50:50 kg/ha. Half dose of nitrogen and full doses of phosphate and potash were applied as basal and remaining 50% Nitrogen were applied in 2

splits at 30 DAS and 45 DAS. Thinning and intercultural operation were done at 15 DAS. Field parameters such as, plant height (cm), number of primary branches plant⁻¹, number of secondary branches plant⁻¹, siliqua number plant⁻¹, 1000 seed weight (g), number of seeds siliqua, seed yield (g plant⁻¹), seed yield (g m⁻²) were recorded at different growth stages of the crop. The data from field experiment related to morphological characters were analyzed following Factorial Randomized Block Design (FRBD) with three replications. Analysis of data was conducted under OPSTAT software programme.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Plant Height (cm)

There was significant variation due to treatment and date of sowing, but non-significant variation was found due to interaction of the two factors. Maximum plant height (cm) at harvest was recorded for T3 (Table 1) with 100.78 cm followed by T1 and T2. Lowest value was recorded in case of T4 (98.69 cm). There was non-significant variation between T1 and T2. Plants sown at normal time (D1) produced maximum plant height (100.13 cm) followed by D3 and D2 where D2 and D3 was statistically at par. However, maximum effect on plant height due to interaction effect was found in D3T3 with 101.34 cm. (Fig. 2)

First Flowering (days)

Table 1 shows that the effect of salicylic acid and sowing date on days to first flowering non significantly influenced by the treatments. Date of sowing significantly influenced this character. For this feature, the interaction between sowing date and treatment was found non-significant. Among the treatments T1 had earliest days to first flowering (50.68 days) followed by T4 (51.11 days) and T3 (51.78 days). Bailey and Bear (1973) demonstrated that early maturity depends

on early flowering. Among date of sowing, very late sowing (D3) showed earliest first flowering with 44.08 days, followed by D2 (47.92 days) and D1 (62.25 days), may be due to higher temperature which reduced the vegetative growth stage. Among the interaction effects (Fig. 3), D3T1 produced earliest days to first flowering (42.33 days).

Fifty Percent Flowering (days)

Fruiting efficiency is determined by the flowering pattern rather than the total number of flowers per plant. [11,13]. There was non-significant variation due to treatment and interaction between date of sowing and treatment (table 1). But date of sowing was found statistically significant for this character. Among all treatments T1 took least time to fifty percent flowering (53.56 days) followed by T4 (54.22 days) and T3 (54.33 days). Among the different date of sowing, D3 took least time to fifty percent flowering with 46.33 days, followed by D2 (50.83 days) and D1 (65.58 days). Since, mustard is a cold loving crop, early sowing increased vegetative growth stages resulting delayed fifty percent flowering. Although, interactions produced non-significant values, D3T1 (Fig. 4) took shortest time to fifty percent flowering (44.67 days).

Hundred Percent Flowering (days)

Table 1 revealed that treatment (T) and interaction effects (DXT) were non-significant, while the mean values showed significant variations among dates of sowing (D). T1 showed the earliest days to hundred percent flowering (56.33 days), followed by T4 (57.11 days) and T3 (57.22 days). T2 had the highest mean days to flowering (57.33 days). Among the date of sowing, D3 had earliest mean number of days to hundred percent flowering with 48.58 days, followed by D2 (53.58 days) and D1 (68.83 days). The non-significant interaction effect of treatment and sowing date (DXT) indicates that the reaction of

salicylic acid at different doses was statistically at par across sowing dates. But in very late sowing D3T1 recorded earliest hundred percent flowering (46.67 days) and D1T2 had the longest flowering period (69.33 days) as depicted in Fig. 5.

Days to Maturity

Data analysis on days to maturity showed that treatment (T) and the interaction between date of sowing and treatment (DXT) were statistically non-significant (Table 1). The effect of date of sowing (D) was found statistically significant for this character. Among all the treatments, T4 took very less time (107.33 days), followed by T1 (107.67 days) and T3 (108 days). Among the different date of sowing, D3 produced earliest maturity with 106 days, followed by D2 (107.50 days) and D1 (109.83 days). Although interaction values (Fig. 6) were non-significant, D3T4 had the shortest maturity period (105.33 days) and D1T3 had the longest maturity period (110.33 days).

Number of Primary Branches Plant⁻¹

While considering the average influence of treatment and date of sowing significant variation was found for both the characters (Table 1). But interaction effect was found non-significant. Among the treatments, T3 produced maximum number of primary branches (5.61) followed by T1 and T4 with non-significant variation between T1 and T4. Least number of primary branches plant⁻¹ (3.92) was recorded in D3 whereas, maximum number of primary branches plant⁻¹ (5.70) was observed in D1 followed by D2 (5.29). Under very late sown (D3) condition, maximum interaction effect was recorded in D3T3. Under normal sown (D1) condition, maximum interaction effect on number of primary branch plant⁻¹ (6.40) was recorded in D1T3 (Fig.7).

Number of Secondary Branches Plant⁻¹

Table 1 demonstrated that treatments and date of sowing had a considerable impact

on the quantity of secondary branches. Significant results were obtained when taking into account the average impact of the date of sowing and treatment. However, there was no significant interaction detected between treatments and date of sowing. Highest number of secondary branches per plant was produced by treatment T3 (4.90), followed by T4 (4.77), and T1 (4.46). The maximum number of secondary branches was produced by D1 (6.26), followed by D2 (4.56) and D3 (2.67). T3D1 interaction (Fig. 8) had highest impact on the number of secondary branches per plant (6.80). Under D3 (very late sown condition), T3 had maximum influence on number of secondary branches (3.03).

Siliqua Number Plant⁻¹

Among the treatments, T3 produced highest number of siliqua plant⁻¹(147.28), followed by T4 (145.26) and T1 (143.50) as depicted in Table 1. T2 produced lowest number of siliqua plant⁻¹ (141.02). Among the different date of sowing, D1 had highest siliqua plant⁻¹ (153.12), followed by D2 (140.51) and D3 (139.17). Significant variation was observed as a result of the date of sowing, treatment and their interaction effect. D1T3, had the greatest interaction effect on siliqua plant⁻¹ with 159.40. Maximum interaction effect due to very late sowing was found in D3T1. However, D3T2, D3T3 and D3T4 were statistically at par for this character (Fig. 9).

Test Weight (g)

Table 1 revealed that the treatment, date of sowing had significant effect on the test weight of Indian mustard. The interaction effect was also found significant. The test weight is a key measure of seed quality since it determines seed potential, sprouting, plant performance, seedling growth. Among the treatments, maximum value for test weight was found in T3 (4.04 g), followed by T2 (3.69 g) and T3 (3.62

g). Minimum test weight was noted in T1 (3.53 g). Plants sown at normal time (D1) produced the maximum test weight (4.02 g), followed by D2 (3.77 g) and D3 (3.38 g). Among the interaction effects, maximum value was observed in D1T3 (4.33 g) followed by D1T4 (4.06 g). There was significant interaction effect during very late sowing (D3), D3T3 followed by D3T2 had maximum influence on test weight (Fig.10) with values 3.74 g and 3.35 g respectively indicating positive influence of salicylic acid on this character.

Number of Seeds Siliqua⁻¹

Number of seeds siliqua⁻¹ is a genetic character which is closely linked to seed yield of a genotype. Table 1 revealed that treatments, date of sowing and their interactions had non-significant effect for this character. The treatment with the maximum number of seeds per siliqua (11.26) was observed in T1. It was followed by T2 and T4 (10.98 and 10.51 respectively). D1 (10.96) produced maximum number of seeds siliqua⁻¹ during normal sowing periods, followed by D2 (10.62) and D3 (10.50). D3T1 (11.87) reported the maximum number of seeds siliqua⁻¹ under very late sowing (Fig. 11). It was followed by D3T2 (10.37) and D3T3 (10.23).

Seed Yield (g plant⁻¹)

In seed production, seed yield is a quantitative characteristic that is impacted by the many yield-contributing characters. Analysis of variance (Table 1) revealed that both treatment and sowing date significantly influenced seed yield. Among the treatments, T3 recorded the highest yield (11.51 g plant⁻¹), followed by T4 (10.86 g plant⁻¹) and T1 (10.80 g plant⁻¹). There was non-significant variation between T1 and T2 but significant variation was observed between T1 and T3. Normal date of sowing i.e. D1 produced maximum seed yield (11.41 g

plant⁻¹), followed by D2 (10.84 g plant⁻¹) and D3 (10.42 g plant⁻¹). Interaction between treatment and date of sowing significantly influenced the character. D1T3 had the maximum interaction effect (11.86 g plant⁻¹). Under very late sowing, D3T3 had the most impact on seed yield (10.88 g plant⁻¹) followed by D3T4 and D3T2 (Fig. 12).

Seed Yield (g m⁻²)

Seed yield (g m⁻²) is most important character, which is influenced by plant population per square meter, number of siliqua per plant, number of seeds per siliqua and 1000 seed weight. Analysis of data presented in Table 1 showed that the treatments, date of sowing, and their interaction had significant impact on the seed yield (g m⁻²). T3 produced the maximum seed yield (282.12 g m⁻²), followed by T2 (269.58 g m⁻²) and T1 (247.01 g m⁻²). There was non-significant variation between T3 and T2 but significant variation was found between T3 and T1. Normal planting time (D1) produced maximum seed yield (294.77 g m⁻²) with a declining trend with delay in planting time. D2 produced 241.31 g m⁻² and D3 produced 225.65 g m⁻². During very late sowing, D3T3 produced maximum interaction effect (267.06 g m⁻²) which differed significantly from D3T2 suggesting greater influence of salicylic acid to avoid heat stress at maturity (Fig. 13).

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Application of Salicylic acid in varying doses resulted higher plant height (cm) when Salicylic acid was sprayed @ 400ppm. Among different dates of sowing, timely sown crop had most impact for this character. The number of primary branches during harvest was maximum when Salicylic acid was sprayed @400ppm and timely sown crop also produced maximum secondary branches. Both treatments and date of sowing significantly influenced

morphological characters like plant height, number of primary branches plant⁻¹, number of secondary branches plant⁻¹, siliqua fresh weight. Number of days to first flowering, fifty percent flowering, hundred percent flowering and days to maturity was significantly influenced due to date of sowing but non-significant influence was found due to treatments and interaction between date of sowing and treatment. T3 (Salicylic acid @400ppm) produced highest number of siliqua plant⁻¹ followed by T4 (Salicylic acid @600ppm). Seed yield (g m⁻²) is an important character which is influenced by yield contributing character such as number of siliqua plant⁻¹, number of seeds siliqua⁻¹ and test weight. In present experiment T3 (Salicylic acid @400ppm) produced maximum seed yield followed by T2 (Salicylic acid @200ppm) and T1 (control) and there was non-significant variation between T3 (Salicylic acid @400ppm) and T2 (Salicylic acid @200ppm). Normal planting produced maximum seed yield with a declined trend with delayed sowing. The maximum seed yield in T3 (Salicylic acid @400ppm) was attributed due to higher number of siliqua plant⁻¹ and test weight.

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Table 1: Flowering, growth and yield attributing characters as influenced by salicylic acid and date of sowing.

Treatments	Plant height (cm)	First flowering (days)	Fifty percent flowering (days)	Hundred percent flowering (days)	Maturity (Days)	Number of primary branches plant ⁻¹	Number of secondary branches plant ⁻¹	Silique number plant ⁻¹	Test weight (g)	Number of seeds siliqua ⁻¹	Seed yield (g plant ⁻¹)	Seed yield (g m ⁻²)
T1	99.23	50.68	53.56	56.33	107.67	4.82	4.46	143.50	3.53	11.26	10.80	247.01
T2	99.09	52.11	54.89	57.33	108.11	4.56	3.88	141.02	3.69	10.98	10.38	269.58
T3	100.78	51.78	54.33	57.22	108.00	5.61	4.90	147.28	4.04	10.02	11.51	282.12
T4	98.69	51.11	54.22	57.11	107.33	4.89	4.77	145.26	3.62	10.51	10.86	216.93
SEm (±)	0.39	0.43	0.46	0.48	0.26	0.15	0.08	0.42	0.07	0.44	0.09	5.56
CD (P=0.05)	1.16	NS	NS	NS	NS	0.44	0.24	1.25	0.19	NS	0.25	16.41
Date of sowing												
D1	100.13	62.25	65.58	68.83	109.83	5.70	6.26	153.12	4.02	10.96	11.41	294.77
D2	98.75	47.92	50.83	53.58	107.50	5.29	4.56	140.51	3.77	10.62	10.84	241.31
D3	99.47	44.08	46.33	48.58	106.00	3.92	2.67	139.17	3.38	10.50	10.42	225.65
SEm (±)	0.33	0.37	0.39	0.42	0.22	0.13	0.07	0.37	0.06	0.38	0.07	4.81
CD (P=0.05)	1.00	1.10	1.12	1.23	0.67	0.38	0.21	1.08	0.17	NS	0.22	14.21
Interactio												

n												
S.Em (±)	0.68	0.75	0.79	0.84	0.45	0.26	0.14	0.73	0.11	0.76	0.15	9.63
CD (P=0.05)	NS	2.16	0.33	NS	0.43	28.42						

Legend: D1-Timely sowing, D2-Late sowing, D3-Very late sowing, T1-Control, T2-Salicylic acid@200ppm, T3-Salicylic acid@400ppm, T4-Salicylic acid@600ppm

Fig. 1: Variation in monthly meteorological observation during the experimental period 2023-24 (November 2023 to March 2024).

Fig. 2: Variation in plant height due to salicylic acid treatment and date of sowing.

Fig. 3: Variation in first flowering (days) due to salicylic acid treatment and date of sowing.

Fig. 4: Variation in 50% flowering (days) due to salicylic acid treatment and date of sowing.

Fig. 5: Variation in 100% flowering (days) due to salicylic acid treatment and date of sowing.

Fig. 6: Variation in days to maturity due to salicylic acid treatment and date of sowing.

Fig. 7: Variation in number of primary branches plant^{-1} due to salicylic acid treatment and date of sowing.

Fig. 8: Variation in number of secondary branches plant^{-1} due to salicylic acid treatment and date of sowing.

Fig. 9: Variation in siliqua number plant⁻¹ due to salicylic acid treatment and date of sowing

Fig. 10: Variation in test weight (g) due to salicylic acid treatment and date of sowing

Fig. 11: Variation in number of seeds siliqua⁻¹ due to salicylic acid treatment and date of sowing.

Fig. 12: Variation in seed yield (g plant⁻¹) due to salicylic acid treatment and date of sowing

Fig. 13: Variation in seed yield (g m⁻²) due to salicylic acid treatment and date of sowing.